

THE PURSUIT OF ADMINISTRATIVE PROBITY THROUGH THE FISCAL RESPONSIBILITY LAW (LC N. 101/2000)^{1 2}

A BUSCA DA PROIBIDADE ADMINISTRATIVA ATRAVÉS DA LEI DE RESPONSABILIDADE FISCAL (LC N. 101/2000)

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ABSTRACT

We developed this study with the aim of presenting the relevance of the Fiscal Responsibility Law (FRL) and the changes occurring on the national scene after its release. The LRF has its genesis in an attempt to solve the existing barriers in the fiscal management of the country as a result of overspending, increasing state indebtedness, lack of planning and transparency in financial and budget management. It was understood, too, that the LRF led to changes in the budgetary institutions, and that through the application of the Principles of Advertising and Transparency seeks such a law effecting a more committed to the aspirations of the community, oriented to the common good management, where public money is spent for the benefit of society, and not to serve self-interest. Finally, we concluded the existence of a close link between the LRF and the Administrative Misconduct Act (LIA), since the latter is applied to penalize the manager, when his acting in violation of the commands of the LRF. This scientific paper was developed through an exploratory literature search, and even a documentary research that led to the analysis of the LRF and the LIA.

Keywords: Fiscal Responsibility Law. Budget. Transparency. Planning. Administrative misconduct.

RESUMO

Elaborou-se o presente estudo com o objetivo de apresentar a relevância da Lei de Responsabilidade Fiscal (LRF) e as transformações ocorridas no cenário nacional após a sua edição. A LRF possui sua gênese na tentativa de solucionar os entraves existentes na gestão fiscal do país, em consequência dos excessivos gastos, do aumento do endividamento do estado, da falta de planejamento e transparência na administração financeira e orçamentária. Entendeu-se, também, que, a LRF acarretou mudanças nas instituições orçamentárias, e que através da aplicação dos Princípios da Publicidade e da Transparência busca tal lei efetivar uma gestão mais comprometida com os anseios da coletividade, orientada para a consecução do bem comum, onde as verbas públicas são aplicadas em proveito da sociedade, e não para atendimento de interesse próprio. Por fim, concluiu-se pela existência de uma estreita ligação entre a LRF e a Lei de Improbidade Administrativa (LIA), vez que esta última é aplicada para penalizar o gestor, quando da sua atuação em desconformidade com os comandos da LRF. Este artigo científico foi desenvolvido por meio de uma pesquisa bibliográfica exploratória, e ainda, uma pesquisa documental que propiciou a análise da LRF e da LIA.

Palavras-Chave: Lei de Responsabilidade Fiscal. Orçamento. Transparência. Planejamento. Improbidade administrativa.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, Brazilian public management has undergone collapses of various kinds, spheres, and levels, violating constitutional and ethical principles, undermining the efficiency of planning, execution, control, and transparency sought in our democratic model through the Fiscal Responsibility Law (FRL) or Supplementary Law No. 101/2000, established in the year two thousand.

Among the significance of this topic, therefore, lies in the fact that the FRL (Law No. 101/2000) was enacted as a way to address the main setbacks of Public Administration, due to frequent irresponsible managements, marked by public debt and the generalized lack of commitment of the public administrator to efficiency, effectiveness, and transparency in their management. In theory, this Law establishes a set of rules that dictate how managers should behave, through more equitable financial, budgetary, and asset management, seeking to avoid public deficits, in order to achieve fiscal balance, through planning, transparency, control, and audit of public expenditures.

Society clamored for changes that would significantly alter the national scene, enabling an action aimed at safeguarding the risks and repairing the deviations that might harm public accounts, and also ensuring that the programming of revenues and expenses were actually carried out in a way that there was an equivalence between both.

Thus, the present scientific paper aims to demonstrate the importance of the Fiscal Responsibility Law (No. 101/2000) in Brazil, focusing and specifying its role in the pursuit of the public manager guided by the Principles of Transparency and Publicity, and having an upright conduct, aiming for an efficient administration, as demanded by the Federal Constitution of 1988.

This scientific paper was developed through exploratory and documentary bibliographic research, which, by encompassing the reading, analysis, and interpretation of the works and laws consulted, proved essential to understand the different scientific contributions available on the topic. A documentary research was also carried out, enabling the analysis of the Fiscal Responsibility Law, FRL, (No. 101/2000) and the Administrative Improbability Law, AIL, (No. 8,429/1992).

For an adequate explanation of the subject, the content of this work was divided into four sections. The first will detail the Fiscal Responsibility Law, presenting its origin and importance for good fiscal management in Brazil. In the second chapter, an analysis will be made regarding the budgetary transformations caused by the FRL. In the third chapter, the role

of the Principles of Publicity and Transparency within the framework of the FRL will be demonstrated; and finally, in the fourth chapter, the relationship between the FRL and AIL will be highlighted.

2 FISCAL RESPONSIBILITY LAW

The Complementary Law (LC) No. 101 of May 2000, commonly referred to as the LRF, was enacted with the intention of establishing a responsible fiscal management system, aiming to balance public accounts, and enhancing transparency and stability in public expenditure. As per Article 1 of the aforementioned law, it "sets standards for public finances towards responsible fiscal management, grounded in Chapter II, Title VI, of the CF (Federal Constitution), which states in its Article 163, I, that it is the duty of the Complementary Law to regulate public finances, and which further mandates in its Article 165, § 9º, I and II:

The Complementary Law shall regulate the fiscal year, its duration, deadlines, the drafting, and organization of the multi-year plan, the budget guidelines law, and the annual budget law. Additionally, it will establish financial and patrimonial management norms for both direct and indirect administration as well as for the creation and operation of funds.⁴

This highlighted legislation, in accordance with its Article 1, §§ 2º and 3º, applies to the Union, States, Federal District, and Municipalities, including the Executive, Legislative, and Judicial branches, as well as the Audit Courts and the Public Prosecutor's Office.

This law was highly anticipated and praised by society, given the belief that it would help curtail public debt by promoting transparency, controlling expenditures, penalizing those who breach it, and enriching the financial and budgetary administration of political entities. LC 101/00 received significant political backing and growing consensus concerning its general principles and guidelines. The State played a pivotal role in its acceptance by widely publicizing the legislation (GREGGIANIN, 2008).

Exorbitant spending on personnel, particularly since 1964, which introduced the so-called "commissioned position" to the Brazilian scene (CALHEIROS, 2013), the excessive resources allocated to public debt payments, and the neoliberal doctrine that was widespread in

⁴ Original text in Portuguese: "Caberá a Lei Complementar, dispor sobre o exercício financeiro, a vigência, os prazos, a elaboração e a organização do plano plurianual, da lei de diretrizes orçamentárias e da lei orçamentária anual, e ainda, estabelecer normas de gestão financeira e patrimonial da administração direta e indireta bem como para a instituição e funcionamento de fundos".

Brazil during the 1990s (GONÇALVES, 2010), influenced the enactment of the LRF. This law mandates that administrators guide their management by efficiency, a requirement further emphasized by Constitutional Amendment (EC) 19/98, which explicitly incorporated the Principle of Efficiency in Public Administration into Article 37 of the Constitution.

The Brazilian context is characterized by a policy of excesses stemming from public asset administrators, resulting in numerous deviations from the State's true role. It's evident there's a disposition towards the privatization of public assets. In this context, the LRF aims to alter this scenario, transitioning from a bureaucratic to a managerial administration (ANDRADE, 2008), striving to streamline public services, improving their delivery, and fostering national economic and social development.

According to Harada (2001, p.230), when public administration is guided by a serious and consequential political project, managers undertake the task of coordinating initiatives to reconcile revenue application with the primary needs and demands of society, establishing goals derived from public interest.

The country currently aligns with a democratic regime, where citizens have the right to actively participate in public administration, supervising and monitoring the actions of managers. A cornerstone of the LRF is the oversight of public spending, which can be carried out by various sectors, including citizens themselves, the Public Prosecutor's Office as the law's watchdog (as per Article 127, CF/88), control entities, Audit Courts, and the Judiciary. The fiscal control in accordance with LC 101/00 is ensured through the actions of internal and external auditing bodies, utilizing public hearings (Article 9º, § 4º and 5º, and Article 48), the Fiscal Management Report (Article 54), the Summarized Budget Execution Report (Article 52), and accountability procedures (LEMOS, 2008).

Article 59 of LC 101/00, concerning the Oversight of Fiscal Management, stipulates:

The Legislative Branch, directly or with the assistance of Audit Courts, and the internal control system of each branch and the Public Prosecutor's Office, will oversee compliance with the norms of this Complementary Law, focusing especially on:

I - achieving the targets set in the budget guidelines law;

II - limits and conditions for carrying out credit operations and registering outstanding commitments;

III - measures adopted for bringing total personnel expenditure back within its respective limit, as stipulated in Articles 22 and 23;

IV - steps taken, as set out in Article 31, to bring the amounts of consolidated and public securities debt back within their respective limits;

V - the allocation of funds obtained from the sale of assets, considering constitutional restrictions and those of this Complementary Law;

VI - compliance with the total expenditure limits of municipal legislatures, when applicable.⁵

According to Afonso (2001, cited by SANTOS FILHO, 2006, p. 6), the objectives of the LRF are: to institute responsible fiscal management, focusing on controlling ongoing expenditure and debt; to prevent deviations and set up correction mechanisms, thereby punishing administrators for severe deviations and for potentially not adopting corrective measures; to deeply transform the Brazilian fiscal regime, introducing a “shock” of transparency to the public sector, making public accounts more widely known while also rendering them more comprehensible.

In accordance with the aforementioned law, in its Article 67, there should be a Fiscal Management Council to continuously oversee and monitor the operationalization of financial administration, which should consist of all the Powers, Ministerial Organ, political entities, and institutions representing society. Its purpose is the adjustment and organization of Federated Entities, through the proliferation of actions that enable greater effectiveness in the application of public funds, in the collection of revenues, and in the control of public debt. Through transparent management, it will need to adopt precepts that will unify public accounts, standardizing them with the balances and statements required by this Law. Furthermore, it must implement clearer principles and rules for smaller Municipalities, and finally, disseminate examinations, studies, and findings on the aspects analyzed by the Council.

Thus, the ten commandments, as listed below from LC 101/00, undeniably facilitate an organization in public finances, with an increase in own revenues, allowing resources to be returned to society in the form of investments in social sectors:

- I – you shall not have budgetary credit with an imprecise purpose nor a limited allocation (art. 5º, § 4º);
- II – you shall not make investments not listed in the PPA (art. 5º, § 5º);
- III – you shall not create nor increase expenses without having resources for their funding (art. 17, §1º);
- IV – you shall not fail to forecast and collect taxes within your jurisdiction (art. 11);
- V – you shall not increase personnel expenses in the last 06 months of your term (art. 21, 11, sole paragraph);

⁵ Original text in Portuguese: “O Poder Legislativo, diretamente ou com o auxílio dos Tribunais de Contas, e o sistema de controle interno de cada Poder e do Ministério Público, fiscalizarão o cumprimento das normas desta Lei Complementar, com ênfase no que se refere a: I - atingimento das metas estabelecidas na lei de diretrizes orçamentárias; II - limites e condições para realização de operações de crédito e inscrição em Restos a Pagar; III - medidas adotadas para o retorno da despesa total com pessoal ao respectivo limite, nos termos dos Arts. 22 e 23; IV - providências tomadas, conforme o disposto no art. 31, para recondução dos montantes das dívidas consolidada e mobiliária aos respectivos limites; V - destinação de recursos obtidos com a alienação de ativos, tendo em vista as restrições constitucionais e as desta Lei Complementar; VI - cumprimento do limite de gastos totais dos legislativos municipais, quando houver”.

- VI – you shall not increase expenses with social security without ensuring its funding source (art. 24);
- VII – you shall not use funds received by transfer for a purpose different from the agreed one (art. 25, § 2º);
- VIII – you shall not undertake obligations with your suppliers for future payment of goods and services (art.37, IV);
- IX – you shall not execute an operation to anticipate Budget Revenue without having settled the previous one (art. 38, VI, “a”);
- X – you shall not use revenue derived from the disposal of assets to finance current expenses (art. 44).⁶ (DEBUS, 2001, p. 61)

The LRF induced a shift in the culture and administrative sphere; thus, breaches of its principles result in the accountability of the manager or individual responsible for delivering public services. The penalties can range across the administrative, civil, and criminal domains. According to the interpretation drawn from Article 73, LC 101/00, violations committed by managers in handling public matters will be penalized in accordance with the Brazilian Penal Code, Law n 1.079/50, pertaining to crimes of responsibility, Decree-Law 201/67, which holds mayors and councilors accountable, and Law n° 8.429/92, LIA.

Having said this, the subsequent changes in budgetary institutions brought about by the LRF will be examined.

3 CHANGES IN BUDGETARY INSTITUTIONS BROUGHT ABOUT BY THE FISCAL RESPONSIBILITY LAW

The 1988 Magna Carta, in its Article 165, I, II, and III, stipulates that “laws initiated by the Executive Branch shall establish: the multi-year plan, budgetary guidelines, and annual budgets”⁷. According to the constitutional norms contained in Article 165:

§5 - The annual budget law shall include:

⁶ Original text in portuguese: “I – não terás crédito orçamentário com finalidade imprecisa nem dotação, limitada (art. 5º, § 4º); II – não farás investimentos que não conste no PPA (art. 5º, § 5º); III – não criarás e nem aumentarás despesas sem que haja recursos para o seu custeio (art. 17, §1º); IV – não deixarás de prever e arrecadar os tributos de tua competência (art. 11); V – não aumentarás a despesa com pessoal nos últimos 06 meses do teu mandato (art. 21, 11, parágrafo único); VI – não aumentarás a despesa com a seguridade social sem que sua fonte de custeio esteja assegurada (art. 24); VII – não utilizarás recursos recebidos por transferência para finalidade diversa da pactuada (art. 25, § 2º); VIII – não assumirás obrigação para com os teus fornecedores, para pagamento a posteriori, de bens e serviços (art.37, IV); IX – não realizarás operação de antecipação da Receita Orçamentária, sem que tenhas liquidada a anterior (art. 38, VI, “a”); X – não utilizarás receita proveniente de alienação de bens, para o financiamento de despesas correntes (art. 44)”.

⁷ Original text in Portuguese: “Leis de iniciativa do Poder Executivo estabelecerão: o plano plurianual, as diretrizes orçamentárias e os orçamentos anuais”.

- I - the fiscal budget relating to the Powers of the Union, its funds, bodies, and entities of direct and indirect administration, including foundations established and maintained by the Public Power;
- II - the investment budget of companies in which the Union, directly or indirectly, holds the majority of the voting share capital;
- III - the social security budget, covering all entities and bodies linked to it, from direct or indirect administration, as well as funds and foundations established and maintained by the Public Power.⁸

The FRL brought about various transformations in the budgetary sphere, such as: a) the introduction of triennial fiscal targets (Article 4, § 1) and a reduction in expenses caused by the three Powers (Articles 19 and 20), b) established norms regulating the transparency and publicity of acts by public managers (Article 48), c) the application of sanctions for non-compliance with the precepts established in the Law (Article 73), d) the prohibition of behaviors deviating from the discipline in the standard, prescription of indebtedness limits (Article 15), and e) made the budgetary system an effective planning mechanism (Articles 4 and 5, LC 101/00 and Article 165, CF/88).

According to the Aurélio Dictionary, planning means preparation work for any enterprise, following a script of determined methods; a process that leads to the establishment of a coordinated set of actions aimed at achieving certain objectives.

One of the main characteristics of planning is the factor related to the dimension of time, meaning, the main feature of planning is the time dimension. It's possible to optimize elements and resources without using the notion of time or duration. For instance, optimizing the number of boxes in a truck's body doesn't require, a priori, the temporal dimension. However, the concept of planning is inseparable from the notion of time.

Among the planning tools, we mention forecast analysis, budgeting, scenarios (from which to choose), probabilities, alternative or emergency solutions (to be prepared in case of obstacles during planning execution), etc.

Planning is also associated with the decision-making process. Planning, to achieve a particular goal in its broadest sense, implies having one or several objectives to be realized along with actions required to successfully complete them. Other, more precise definitions include that planning is a decision-making process to achieve a desired future, considering the current situation and the internal and external factors that might influence the success of the

⁸ Original text in Portuguese: “§ 5º - A lei orçamentária anual compreenderá: I - o orçamento fiscal referente aos Poderes da União, seus fundos, órgãos e entidades da administração direta e indireta, inclusive fundações instituídas e mantidas pelo Poder Público; II - o orçamento de investimento das empresas em que a União, direta ou indiretamente, detenha a maioria do capital social com direito a voto; III - o orçamento da seguridade social, abrangendo todas as entidades e órgãos a ela vinculados, da administração direta ou indireta, bem como os fundos e fundações instituídos e mantidos pelo Poder Público”.

objectives. It ranges from simple to complex, depending on the means used. The action of planning in management refers to plans and projects in their different scopes, levels, and attitudes.

Planning is also analyzed from the perspective of organizing necessary activities and can be understood as a skill. Planning (also referred to as premeditation) is the process of thinking about and organizing the activities required to achieve a desired goal. It involves creating and maintaining a plan, including psychological aspects that require conceptual skills. There are even a couple of tests to measure someone's planning capability. As such, planning is a fundamental property of intelligent behavior.

Planning plays a prominent role in the FRL, as the administrator, representing the Public Power, must incur obligations in proportion to the public budget's capacity, setting plans and performance targets throughout the year or even multiple years.

A significant step in budgetary development was the inclusion of the Fiscal Targets Annex, which has triennial targets related to revenues, expenses, primary and nominal results of public debt (Article 4, §1), (NUNES S.; NUNES R., 2002, p.19). Another achievement was the preparation of the budget, which must detail expenses with their respective revenues, and bimonthly publication of collection targets (Article 13) and monthly financial planning (NUNES S.; NUNES R., 2002, p. 21).

The Law in question also requires an analysis of the social security situation and public funds, necessitating an annex detailing the use of privatization funds and another Fiscal Risks Annex, showing potential administration challenges and possible obligations subject to future events.

The Supreme Law dictates in its Article 165, § 3, that “the Executive Power shall publish, within thirty days following the end of each bimonthly period, a summarized report of the budget execution”⁹, and according to Article 52, I and II of LC 101/00, this report will consist of:

- I - budget balance, which will specify, by economic category, the: a) revenues by source, informing those realized and to be realized, as well as the updated forecast; b) expenses by nature group, detailing the allocation for the fiscal year, the expense settled, and the balance;
- II - statements of execution for: a) revenues, by economic category and source, specifying the initial forecast, the updated forecast for the fiscal year, revenue realized in the bimonthly period, revenue realized in the fiscal year, and forecast to be realized; b) expenses, by economic category and nature group of the expense, detailing the

⁹ Original text in Portuguese: “o Poder Executivo publicará, até trinta dias após o encerramento de cada bimestre, relatório resumido da execução orçamentária”.

initial allocation, allocation for the fiscal year, committed and settled expenses, in the bimonthly period and in the fiscal year; c) expenses, by function and subfunction.¹⁰

Concerned about the possibility of contracts being made outside the budgetary process, Article 37 of the FRL establishes that the following practices are equivalent to credit operations and are prohibited:

- I - Securing of funds by means of anticipating revenue from taxes or contributions whose generating event has not yet occurred, without prejudice to the provisions in § 7 of art. 150 of the Constitution;
- II - Advance receipt of funds from a company in which the Public Power holds, directly or indirectly, the majority of voting capital stock, except for profits and dividends, in accordance with the law;
- III - Direct assumption of commitment, debt acknowledgment, or similar operation with suppliers of goods, merchandise, or services, through the issuance, acceptance, or endorsement of credit titles, this prohibition not applying to dependent state-owned companies;
- IV - Undertaking of obligations, without budgetary authorization, with suppliers for subsequent payment for goods and services¹¹.

With the aim of preventing the public administrator from incurring debts in the last year of their term that they cannot fulfill, which will consequently be due in the following fiscal year, the Fiscal Responsibility Law (LRF) included in its text, article 42, which prohibits the public administrator from incurring liabilities in the eight months prior to the end of their term that cannot be met within this period or that have installments to be paid in the following year without sufficient funds for their settlement.

In the pursuit of financial balance, the LRF introduced numerous provisions related to the end of the term, regarding personnel expenses, during the last six months of the term, no action that leads to the increase of these expenses can be taken. Should this rule be violated, the administrator will be penalized in proportion to their responsibility.

¹⁰ Original text in Portuguese: “I - balanço orçamentário, que especificará, por categoria econômica, as: a) receitas por fonte, informando as realizadas e a realizar, bem como a previsão atualizada; b) despesas por grupo de natureza, discriminando a dotação para o exercício, a despesa liquidada e o saldo; II - demonstrativos da execução as: a) receitas, por categoria econômica e fonte, especificando a previsão inicial, a previsão atualizada para o exercício, a receita realizada no bimestre, a realizada no exercício e a previsão a realizar; b) despesas, por categoria econômica e grupo de natureza da despesa, discriminando dotação inicial, dotação para o exercício, despesas empenhada e liquidada, no bimestre e no exercício; c) despesas, por função e subfunção”.

¹¹ Original text in Portuguese: “I - Captação de recursos a título de antecipação de receita de tributo ou contribuição cujo fato gerador ainda não tenha ocorrido, sem prejuízo do disposto no § 7o do art. 150 da Constituição; II - Recebimento antecipado de valores de empresa em que o Poder Público detenha, direta ou indiretamente, a maioria do capital social com direito a voto, salvo lucros e dividendos, na forma da legislação; III - Assunção direta de compromisso, confissão de dívida ou operação assemelhada, com fornecedor de bens, mercadorias ou serviços, mediante emissão, aceite ou aval de título de crédito, não se aplicando esta vedação a empresas estatais dependentes; IV - assunção de obrigação, sem autorização orçamentária, com fornecedores para pagamento a posteriori de bens e serviços”.

Should there be non-compliance with the prohibitions set out in the LRF, the actions taken will be annulled, either by their invalidation or by the amortization of the debt, or even by the establishment of a fund allocated for the payment of obligations of the following fiscal year.

Concerned about breaches of fiscal responsibility standards, the legislator listed some sanctions in the event of non-compliance, such as: cessation of voluntary transfers, prohibition from obtaining guarantees directly or indirectly from another entity, and prohibition from incurring credit operations, except those related to the refinancing of public debt and those aimed at reducing personnel expenses.

The LRF was established to assure society the possibility of a participative and transparent administration, allowing the public to oversee the work of the administrator, demanding democratic and law-abiding action, controlling public expenditure, requiring the budget to reflect social reality, and that revenues are effectively applied in the areas they are intended for. It is not just an assortment of articles but a coherent set of norms aimed at the development of society through planned and effective management (ANDRADE, 2008).

Subsequently, the Principles of Publicity and Transparency and their influence on public management will be analyzed.

4 PRINCIPLES OF PUBLICITY AND TRANSPARENCY

Principles represent essential legal standards within a juridical apparatus, characterized by a high axiological degree, and thus, hierarchically superior to other norms. They expand in either a comprehensive or contained manner within systems, serving as their foundation and providing logical, concise, and balanced continuity (CUNHA JUNIOR, 2010).

According to the esteemed scholar Mello (2004, cited by CUNHA JUNIOR, 2010, p. 35), a principle is the core mandate of a system, its true foundation, a fundamental provision that radiates over different norms, forming their essence and serving as a criterion for their precise understanding. This is mainly because it defines the logic and rationality of normative systems, bestowing upon them coherence and harmonious meaning. The knowledge of these principles governs the interpretation of the different parts that make up the cohesive entity referred to as the juridical system.

Article 37 of the CF enumerates, in an illustrative manner, some principles specific to Direct and Indirect Public Administration. These are legality, impersonality, morality,

publicity, and efficiency. They guide managers in their actions, ensuring effective management, geared towards the appropriate use of public funds in line with social interests (CALHEIROS, 2013).

The LRF emphasizes the Principles of Publicity and Transparency as paramount for management focused on meeting societal needs, through responsible administration regarding public finances, as stipulated in its Article 1, § 1º:

Responsibility in fiscal management presupposes planned and transparent action that prevents risks and corrects deviations that could disrupt the balance of public accounts. This is achieved by adhering to goals that balance revenues and expenses and by obeying limits and conditions concerning revenue waiver, personnel expenses, social security, consolidated and mobile debts, credit operations (including advanced revenue), guarantee concessions, and pending payment registrations.¹²

Regarding Publicity, it is recognized as a fundamental right of the individual, deeply linked to the democratic principle (MOTTA, 2008). According to (MELLO, 2007, p.110), this enshrines the administrative duty to maintain full transparency in its actions.

The CF regulates in its Article 37, § 1º, concerning Publicity:

§ 1º - The publicity of acts, programs, works, services, and campaigns of public bodies must be educational, informative, or provide social guidance. It should not contain names, symbols, or images that characterize personal promotion of authorities or public servants.¹³

Thus, in light of Article 37, caput, of the 1988 Federal Constitution, the Minister of the Supreme Federal Court, Celso de Mello, in MS nº 24.725 MC/DF (MOTTA, 2008) argues that the constitutional postulates of publicity, morality, and responsibility - inseparable from the directive that establishes the republican practice of power - do not allow matters, such as the allocation, use, and proof of expenses related to public resources, to be placed under an unthinkable confidentiality regime. It's worth recalling that the power statutes, in a Republic founded on democratic bases, cannot privilege mystery. The political-legal legitimacy of the democratic order, imbued with the necessary ethical substrate, is only compatible with a visible

¹² Original text in Portuguese: “A responsabilidade na gestão fiscal pressupõe a ação planejada e transparente, em que se previnem risco e corrigem desvios capazes de afetar o equilíbrio das contas públicas, mediante o cumprimento de metas de resultados entre receitas e despesas e a obediência a limites e condições no que tange a renúncia de receita, geração de despesas com pessoal, da seguridade social de outras, dívidas consolidada e mobiliária, operações de crédito, inclusive por antecipação de receita, concessão de garantia e inscrições em Restos a Pagar”.

¹³ Original text in Portuguese: “§ 1º - A publicidade dos atos, programas, obras, serviços e campanhas dos órgãos públicos deverá ter caráter educativo, informativo ou de orientação social, dela não podendo constar nomes, símbolos ou imagens que caracterizem promoção pessoal de autoridades ou servidores públicos”.

power regime. By desacralizing secrecy, Brazil's new Constitution restored the old republican dogma and fully exposed the State to the democratic principle of publicity. This principle, in rejecting any commitment to mystery, serves as a factor legitimizing governmental decisions and actions. The new Brazilian political statute, which rejects concealed power, recognizes the publicity of state acts and activities as an expressive constitutional value. This value is so significant that it's included in the list of rights, guarantees, and fundamental freedoms (RTJ 139/712-713).

Conversely, transparency is characterized by clarity and is the opposite of obscurity. The LRF, by enshrining it in its articles, aimed to facilitate the understanding of public acts.

Fiscal Transparency is construed as an implied constitutional principle that seeks to ensure financial action is clear, open, and unreserved, targeting both the community and the State. It serves as the guiding tool for the budget and responsible administration (TORRES, 2000).

The LRF emphasizes in its text certain provisions reflecting the demand for transparency in public management. For example, Section I of Chapter IX, titled "Transparency of Fiscal Management," mentions in Article 48 the participation and holding of public hearings. Article 49 dictates that the accounts presented by the Chief Executive should be available for public consultation and evaluation, and Article 50, § 3º, mandates the maintenance of a cost system, enabling the monitoring and analysis of the administration.

The Fiscal Management Report addresses the four primary factors in the LRF, namely: planning, transparency, control, and accountability, as stipulated in Article 54. Lima states that the core objective of this law is to strengthen fundamental public administration concepts. It seeks a transparent and responsible management of government resources, emphasizing planning (multi-year plan, budgetary guidelines law, and annual budget law), controlling fiscal management by setting targets for results assessment, and publicizing public accounts. This approach is centered on the tripod: revenue – expense – debt (2012, p.30).

The Principles of Publicity and Transparency are intertwined, as the former serves as a means to realize the latter, evident in Article 48 of the LRF:

Tools for fiscal management transparency, which will be widely disseminated, including through public electronic means, are the plans, budgets, and budgetary guideline laws; the account statements and their preliminary opinions; the Summary Report of Budget Execution and the Fiscal Management Report; and simplified versions of these documents.¹⁴

¹⁴ Original text in Portuguese: “São instrumentos de transparência da gestão fiscal, aos quais será dada ampla divulgação, inclusive em meios eletrônicos de acesso público: os planos, orçamentos e leis de diretrizes

Principles establish the values that guide the legal order, such as democracy, freedom, equality, legal certainty, dignity, rule of law, among others. They play the role of guiding the true understanding, hermeneutics, and application of the law, also serving as a basis for other sources of law (CUNHA JUNIOR, 2010).

Subsequently, the LRF and its relation to the LIA will be analyzed.

5 FISCAL RESPONSIBILITY LAW AND ADMINISTRATIVE IMPROBITY LAW

According to the Aurélio dictionary, improbity means “without probity, dishonest” and to be *probo* is “of integral character, honored”. It consists of the individual's conduct of acting ethically, dignifiedly, and according to legal dictates.

The Magna Carta, regarding the defense of integrity in Public Administration, plays a prominent role, as Article 37, as previously seen, lists the Principle of Morality in public management, clearly showing society's concern for defending probity, ethics, and honesty in Public Administration (CUNHA JUNIOR, 2010).

The Principle of Morality is an affirmation made by the constitutional legislator so that the public administrator bases his conduct on this corollary (MELLO, 2007, p. 115).

The Administration and its agents must act in conformity with ethical principles. Violating them will mean violating the Law itself, constituting unlawfulness subjecting the tainted conduct to invalidation, as this principle has taken on a legal forum as per Art. 37 of the Constitution. This includes, evidently, the so-called principles of loyalty and good faith, so aptly emphasized by the Spanish master Jesús Gonzalés Perez in his precious monograph. According to the canons of loyalty and good faith, the Administration must act towards its citizens with sincerity and clarity, prohibiting any cunning behavior tainted with malice designed to confuse or hinder citizens' rights.

There are various provisions in the Constitution about Administrative Improbity. Article 15, item V of the CF highlights the causes for the suspension of political rights and cites improbity as one of the possibilities; Article 37, §4 of the Magna Carta emphasizes penalties for those who commit acts of improbity (CUNHA JUNIOR, 2010), namely: suspension of political rights, loss of public function, unavailability of goods, and reimbursement to the

orçamentárias; as prestações de contas e o respectivo parecer prévio; o Relatório Resumido da Execução Orçamentária e o Relatório de Gestão Fiscal; e as versões simplificadas desses documentos”.

treasury, as listed in the law, without detriment to any penal action that may be filed. The Constitution, in Article 97, §10, item III, also states:

§10. In case of untimely release of the resources mentioned in item II of §1 and §§2 and 6 of this article:
III - the head of the Executive Branch will answer according to the fiscal responsibility legislation and the administrative improbity law;¹⁵

Other constitutional norms related to improbity are found in: a) §9 of Article 14, which establishes that LC will define other forms of ineligibility and the timeframes for their termination, aiming to safeguard administrative probity and morality when executing the mandate, considering certain factors such as the candidate's prior conduct and the legitimacy and normality of elections, opposing the influence of economic power or excessive performance in a direct or indirect administration role; b) Article 85, item V, which states that the actions of the President of the Republic that act against the Brazilian Constitution, especially acting in disagreement with administrative probity, constitute a crime of responsibility; c) §3, item III of Article 37, which mandates that legislation will address the means by which the user will participate in direct and indirect public management, especially establishing “the discipline of representation against the negligent or abusive exercise of public office, employment, or function”¹⁶.

The enactment of Law 8249/92 aimed to penalize managers who do not act properly, using public assets for personal enrichment or failing to act with the diligence society expects (VIEIRA, 2001). This Law defines situations in which acts of improbity occur: acts that result in illicit enrichment (Article 9), those causing damage to the treasury (Article 10), and those that violate the principles of public administration (Article 11). It also specifies the active and passive subjects and the applicable sanctions in the defined scenarios. The active and passive subjects of the acts of administrative improbity are those listed in Article 1 of Law 8249/92:

Public agents, whether employees or not, who commit acts against the direct, indirect, or foundational administration of any of the political entities' Powers, of the Territory, of a company incorporated into public assets, or of an institution that the public power has founded or funded with more than fifty percent of the assets or annual revenue.¹⁷

¹⁵ Original text in Portuguese: “§ 10. No caso de não liberação tempestiva dos recursos de que tratam o inciso II do § 1º e os §§ 2º e 6º deste artigo: III - o chefe do Poder Executivo responderá na forma da legislação de responsabilidade fiscal e de improbidade administrativa;”.

¹⁶ Original text in Portuguese: “A disciplina da representação contra o exercício negligente ou abusivo de cargo, emprego ou função pública”.

¹⁷ Original text in Portuguese: “Os agentes públicos, servidor ou não, que cometam atos em desfavor da administração direta, indireta ou fundacional de qualquer dos Poderes dos entes políticos, do Território, de empresa agrupada ao patrimônio público ou ainda, de instituto em que o poder público tenha fundado ou custeado com mais de cinquenta por cento do patrimônio ou da receita anual;”.

Included in this relation, according to the unique paragraph of Article 1, are organizations that receive tax or credit subsidies from public entities, and entities funded with less than fifty percent of the assets or annual revenue. However, in this situation, the penalty will only apply up to the amount that public funds have contributed.

The LRF (Fiscal Responsibility Law) and LIA (Administrative Improbability Law) complement each other and aim to punish and restrict irresponsible management. The concept of citizenship in the LRF is evident as it seeks to control public spending. The LRF aims to achieve a proba management through a “shock of morality” when handling public assets, using procedures that describe how the manager should act in the handling of public matters, always guiding their actions by responsibility, transparency, efficiency, and administrative morality (VIEIRA, 2001).

The relationship of the LIA with the LRF is evident through Article 73 of the latter, which explicitly states that the LIA will be applied in the employment of sanctions (FIGUEIREDO, 2001). Moreover, issues related to administrative-financial law in the LIA are closely related to the LRF, as seen in subsections VI, VII, VIII, IX, X, and XI of Article 10 of the LIA, as follows:

Art. 10. Constitutes an act of administrative improbity that causes damage to the treasury any action or omission, intentional or negligent, that results in financial loss, diversion, appropriation, waste, or dilapidation of assets or goods of the entities referred to in Article 1 of this law, especially:

VI - carrying out a financial operation without observing legal and regulatory norms or accepting insufficient or unsuitable guarantees;

VII - granting administrative or fiscal benefits without observing the legal or regulatory formalities applicable to the type;

VIII - thwarting the legality of a bidding process or improperly waiving it;

IX - ordering or allowing unauthorized expenses;

X - acting negligently in the collection of taxes or revenue, as well as regarding the conservation of public property;

XI - releasing public funds without strict observance of relevant standards or influencing in any way their irregular application;¹⁸

¹⁸ Original text in Portuguese: “Art. 10. Constitui ato de improbidade administrativa que causa lesão ao erário qualquer ação ou omissão, dolosa ou culposa, que enseje perda patrimonial, desvio, apropriação, malbaratamento ou dilapidação dos bens ou haveres das entidades referidas no art. 1º desta lei, e notadamente: VI - realizar operação financeira sem observância das normas legais e regulamentares ou aceitar garantia insuficiente ou inidônea; VII - conceder benefício administrativo ou fiscal sem a observância das formalidades legais ou regulamentares aplicáveis à espécie; VIII - frustrar a licitude de processo licitatório ou dispensá-lo indevidamente; IX - ordenar ou permitir a realização de despesas não autorizadas em lei ou regulamento; X - agir negligentemente na arrecadação de tributo ou renda, bem como no que diz respeito à conservação do patrimônio público; XI - liberar verba pública sem a estrita observância das normas pertinentes ou influir de qualquer forma para a sua aplicação irregular;”.

Article 11 of the LIA, which deals with acts of improbity against the principles of Public Administration, when by omission or commission they violate the duties of honesty, impartiality, legality, and loyalty to institutions, are linked to fiscal responsibility, subsection II, which consists of delaying or omitting an act that should have been performed ex officio; subsection IV, which denies publicity to public acts, principles enshrined in the CF and also in the LRF, and the corollary of transparency in public management; subsection VI, failing to account when required.

The legislation in question lists the penalties due to those who commit acts that go against administrative probity, and that are related to the LRF. The sanctions will be applied either individually or cumulatively, taking into account the gravity of the crime, and they are not subordinate to the criminal, civil, and administrative punishments, which are regulated by specific law, as understood in Article 12 of the LIA, subsections II and III, and the sole paragraph, as follows:

II - in the case of Art. 10, full compensation for the damage, loss of assets or values illicitly added to the estate, loss of public function, suspension of political rights from five to eight years, payment of a civil fine of up to twice the damage value and prohibition to contract with the Public Power or receive fiscal or credit benefits, directly or indirectly, even through a legal entity in which they are the majority shareholder, for a period of five years;

III - in the case of Art. 11, full compensation for the damage, if any, loss of public function, suspension of political rights from three to five years, payment of a civil fine up to a hundred times the value of the remuneration perceived by the agent and prohibition to contract with the Public Power or receive fiscal or credit benefits, directly or indirectly, even through a legal entity in which they are the majority shareholder, for a period of three years.

Sole paragraph. In setting the penalties provided for in this law, the judge will take into account the extent of the damage caused, as well as the financial benefit obtained by the agent.¹⁹

The proper use of public resources depends on the integrity of the manager and those involved in the execution of the public task. Whether they are honest or dishonest, proba or improba, is independent of legislation; what can happen is the warning of applying a sanction (HARADA, 2001).

¹⁹ Original text in Portuguese: “II - na hipótese do art. 10, ressarcimento integral do dano, perda dos bens ou valores acrescidos ilicitamente ao patrimônio, se concorrer esta circunstância, perda da função pública, suspensão dos direitos políticos de cinco a oito anos, pagamento de multa civil de até duas vezes o valor do dano e proibição de contratar com o Poder Público ou receber benefícios ou incentivos fiscais ou creditícios, direta ou indiretamente, ainda que por intermédio de pessoa jurídica da qual seja sócio majoritário, pelo prazo de cinco anos; III - na hipótese do art. 11, ressarcimento integral do dano, se houver, perda da função pública, suspensão dos direitos políticos de três a cinco anos, pagamento de multa civil de até cem vezes o valor da remuneração percebida pelo agente e proibição de contratar com o Poder Público ou receber benefícios ou incentivos fiscais ou creditícios, direta ou indiretamente, ainda que por intermédio de pessoa jurídica da qual seja sócio majoritário, pelo prazo de três anos. Parágrafo único. Na fixação das penas previstas nesta lei o juiz levará em conta a extensão do dano causado, assim como o proveito patrimonial obtido pelo agente”.

The issue surrounding the penalties imposed by the LIA is linked to society's desire to see a change in the country's landscape. People are not satisfied with just seeing the irresponsible and dishonest manager imprisoned. They wish for the punishment to be just, considering the damage caused to the public estate, reimbursing the public coffers for everything improperly taken (RAFANHIM, 2006). This proactive attitude ensures that the Brazilian State honors the principles inscribed in the Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil, known as the Citizens' Constitution, which calls for a public administration guided by action according to the law, action by the administrator without discrimination or favoritism, according to ethical and moral principles, transparency in its actions, and, finally, through the consistent use of the tools it has to achieve its objectives.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The Fiscal Responsibility Law (LRF) was a significant achievement for Brazilian society. At the time of its enactment, the country was experiencing rampant mismanagement, public debt, unchecked spending, and poor stewardship of public assets. The LRF emerged as a solution to these numerous challenges.

The law in question lays out plans and objectives that public administrators must adhere to, aiming for financial and budgetary balance. Officials must adhere strictly to these stipulated goals; otherwise, they may face penalties in administrative, civil, and even criminal realms.

The purpose of this study was to highlight the significance of this law for the country and the innovations that came with its drafting. In this context, it's understood that the LRF led to various budgetary transformations, such as: a) the introduction of fiscal goals and reduced spending by all three branches of government; b) establishing rules ensuring transparency and publicity of officials' actions; c) the enforcement of penalties for non-compliance with the LRF's stipulations; d) prohibiting behaviors diverging from the regulation, setting debt limits; e) transforming the budgetary system into an efficient planning mechanism; and f) regulating the commitment of obligations at the end of a term, setting restrictions and prohibitions.

This study analyzed the Principles of Publicity and Transparency and their influence on public management. The LRF provides society with an opportunity for transparent and participatory management, allowing citizens to oversee administrators' activities. It's clear that these principles are expressly found in the LRF. For instance, Section I of Chapter IX is titled "On fiscal management transparency." Article 48 emphasizes public participation and the

holding of public hearings; Article 49 mandates the accounts submitted by the Executive Chief be available for public consultation and appreciation; and Article 50, §3, prescribes a cost system to monitor and analyze management.

Moreover, it was demonstrated that the principles of Publicity and Transparency are interconnected. Publicity serves as a means to achieve transparency, as evident in Article 48 of the LRF.

This academic article also explored the relationship between the LRF and the Administrative Improbity Act (LIA). The latter penalizes dishonest administrators, particularly those who act unethically. Thus, irresponsible and corrupt administrators will face personal penalties, including returning all misappropriated public assets.

Given the evidence, the importance of the LRF for Brazil is undeniable. It transformed public administration by rationalizing public expenditures and the resulting national debt, emphasizing planning as a key development tool through goal-setting, enhancing fiscal and budgetary control through public oversight and official agencies, highlighting the principles of transparency and publicity in public spending, and lastly, setting out sanctions for those administrators acting irresponsibly in their public duties.

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